

A facile route to *N*-fused pyrrole lactams

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N-Fused pyrrole lactams (1a-d) were prepared by substitution and cyclization of methyl 1-(2-bromoethane)pyrrole carboxylate in one-pot. The latter was obtained by treatment of methyl pyrrole-2-carboxylate with excess 1,2-dibromoethane containing NaOH in the presences of PTC.

(*1H*)-3,4-Dihydropyrro[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-1-one and its *N*-methyl derivatives possess a variety of interesting biological activities¹. Recently, many alkaloids with the polycyclic framework consisting of a fused pyrrolopyrazine have been separated from marine sponges². We have found that some acyl derivatives of (*1H*)-3,4-dihydropyrro[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-1-one possess remarkable anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities³. The interest in extending the study of new potent anti-inflammatory and analgesic agents led us to investigate the synthesis of *N*-acyl derivatives of (*1H*)-3,4-dihydropyrro[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-1-one (1a-d).

The lactam 1a has been prepared by three routes : (i) by a Beckmann rearrangement of 1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone with polyphosphoric acid at 170–180° (Scheme 1)¹, (ii) by substitution and cyclization of methyl 1-(2-bromoethane)pyrrole-2-carboxylate 2 (Scheme 2) or (iii) by selective reduction and cyclization of methyl 1-(cyanomethyl)pyrrole-2-carboxylate (Scheme 3)⁴. The route involved in 2 seemed very simple and rational, but our attempts to repeat the procedure for synthesis of 2 gave poor result. An improved method of synthesis of 2 and an approach to lactams (1a-d) were therefore sought which were simple

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

and convenient. We now report an approach that contains improved method of synthesis of **2** and a facile route to pyrrole lactams.

Starting material methyl pyrrole-2-carboxylate (Scheme 2) was prepared by the reported method⁵. We have found that compound **2** was easily obtained by methyl pyrrole-2-carboxylate *N*-alkylation with excess 1,2-dibromoethane containing NaOH in the presence of PTC in high yield. Thus, a mixture of methyl pyrrole-2-carboxylate, 50% sodium hydroxide (3 equiv) and tetrabutylammonium bromide (1 equiv) in 1,2-dibromoethane (5 equiv) was stirred at room temperature for 0.5 h. Compound **2** was obtained in 95% yield after purifying by column chromatography on silica gel. When the amount of PTC decreased to 0.2 equiv, the reaction completed in about 6 h. Using dichloromethane instead of 1,2-dibromoethane produced compound **3**, not expected methyl 1-chloromethyl-2-carboxylate. The result shows that methyl 1-chloromethyl-2-carboxylate undergoes *N*-alkylation more rapidly than dichloromethane.

Reacting of **2** with excess methylamine in acetonitrile containing cat. amount of KI gave the lactam **1a**. Reactions between **2** and other alkylamines were examined under these conditions (Table 1). When aromatic amines were used instead of alkyl amines, the reactions did not occur. This result may be partly explained by the lower substituted activity of aromatic amines, caused by the conjugating system between N with phenyl cyclic.

Easy reaction of methyl pyrrole-2-carboxylate and 1,2-dibromoethane in the presences of PTC may provide a simple method to *N*-alkylation of pyrrole derivatives. The substitution of methyl 1-(2-bromoethane)-2-carboxylate with alkylamines and then intramolecular cyclization show a facile route to *N*-fused lactams.

Table 1. The results of reactions

Compd. no.	Method	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	CH ₃ NH ₂ /CH ₃ CN(cat. KI)/50°/30 h	125–126	75 ^a
1b	C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂ /CH ₃ CN(cat. KI)/50°/30 h	40–41	71 ^b
1c	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇ NH ₂ /CH ₃ CN(cat. KI)/50°/30 h	35–36	65 ^a
1d	<i>i</i> -C ₃ H ₇ NH ₂ /CH ₃ CN(cat. KI)/50°/30 h	Oil	58 ^c
2	BrCH ₂ CH ₂ Br/PTC/25°/30 h	Oil	95 ^c
3	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /PTC/25°/30 h	144–146	82 ^c

^aRecrystallized from ethyl acetate/hexane. ^bRecrystallized from water.

^cPurified by column chromatography on silica-gel.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined using a Yanaco instrument and

are uncorrected. NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker ARX-300 instrument (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Shimadzu GCMS-QP5050A spectrometer. The elemental analyses were carried out using a Carid Erba-1106 analyzer.

Compound 1a (Found : C, 63.95; H, 6.69; N, 18.68. C₈H₁₀N₂O calcd. for : C, 63.97; H, 6.71; N, 18.66%); *m/z* 150 (M⁺, 100%), 122, 107, 94, 79, 52, 39, 28; δ_H 3.11 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 3.66 (2H, t, *J* 5.85 Hz, 3-CH₂), 4.16 (2H, t, *J* 5.88 Hz, 4-CH₂), 6.22 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.72, *J*_{6,7} 2.58 Hz, 7-H), 6.71 (1H, m, 6-H), 6.93 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.72, *J*_{6,8} 1.48 Hz, 8-H); δ_C 33.6, 43.2, 47.8, 109.4, 112.6, 122.5, 124.5, 159.7; **1b** : *m/z* 164 (M⁺, 100%), 149, 136, 122, 107, 94, 79, 52, 39, 28; δ_H 1.22 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.63 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.69 (2H, t, *J* 5.82 Hz, 3-H), 4.16 (2H, t, *J* 5.80 Hz, 4-H), 6.24 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.68, *J*_{6,7} 2.56 Hz, 7-H), 6.73 (1H, m, 6-H), 6.95 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.68, *J*_{6,8} 1.45 Hz, 8-H); δ_C 12.7, 40.9, 43.7, 45.4, 109.7, 113.1, 122.5, 125.0, 159.3; **1c** : *m/z* 178 (M⁺), 163, 149 (100%), 136, 121, 107, 94, 79, 65, 52, 39, 27; δ_H 0.95 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.62 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 3.50 (2H, t, CH₂CH₂CH₃), 3.65 (2H, t, *J* 5.88 Hz, 3-H), 4.13 (2H, t, *J* 5.87 Hz, 4-H), 6.21 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.70, *J*_{6,7} 2.58 Hz, 7-H), 6.70 (1H, m, 6-H), 6.91 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.70, *J*_{6,8} 1.47 Hz, 8-H); **1d** : *m/z* 178 (M⁺, 100%); δ_H 1.20 (6H, d, CH(CH₃)₂), 3.57 (2H, t, *J* 5.83 Hz, 3-H), 4.12 (2H, t, *J* 5.82 Hz, 4-H), 5.03 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 6.23 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 2.48 Hz, 7-H), 6.72 (1H, m, 6-H), 6.93 (1H, dd, *J*_{7,8} 3.72, *J*_{6,8} 1.42 Hz, 8-H).

Compound 3 (Found : C, 59.51; H, 5.36; N, 10.70. C₁₃H₁₄N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 59.53; H, 5.38; N, 10.68%); *m/z* 262 (M⁺, 100%); δ_H 3.85 (6H, s, OCH₃), 6.12 (2H, m), 6.94 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.97 (2H, m), 7.31 (2H, m).

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